

Zenodo RESILIENCE Community Upload Guide

Overview

This guide explains how to upload RESILIENCE deliverables and related outputs to the RESILIENCE Zenodo community. It outlines required metadata, optional fields that improve discoverability, and RESILIENCE-specific conventions such as the resource type, versioning conventions, and the mandatory grant link. By following this guide, you help ensure consistency across our outputs, improving their discoverability and FAIRness.

Prerequisites

To follow along with this guide, you need:

- Your own Zenodo account. See their documentation on [how to register](#) if you don't have one.
- The file(s) you want to upload.

Start a New Upload

First, go to the [RESILIENCE Zenodo community webpage](#). Then click the 'New upload' button.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for the RESILIENCE community. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The user 'marte.del...' is logged in. The main header displays the community name 'RESILIENCE - Religious Studies Infrastructure: tooLs, Innovation, Experts, conNections and Centres in Europe' along with a 'New upload' button. Below the header, there are tabs for 'Records', 'Requests', 'Members', 'Curation policy', and 'About'. The 'Records' tab is active, showing 6 results found. A 'Sort by' dropdown is set to 'Newest'. The first result is a presentation titled 'RESILIENCE Presentation on RDM and the D2.4 Data Management Plan' by De Leeuw, Marte, with a 'Presentation' tag and an 'Open' status. The description mentions it is part of the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project (PPP) and outlines recommended practices for data management. The record is from the 'Part of EU Open Research Repository' and was uploaded on October 24, 2024.

Add Your File(s)

Drag your file(s) into the upload area or select them manually

Tip: Uploads must begin from the community page to ensure the record is automatically submitted for review and published in the RESILIENCE community. If not, you can still select a community at the top of your 'New Upload' page.

Complete the Basic Metadata

Fill in all mandatory fields:

- Resource Type – for RESILIENCE deliverables, select 'Publication / Project deliverable'
- Title
- Publication date – this automatically sets to the current date so only change if uploading an old document
- Creators – use an identifier such as an ORCID ID to make the upload appear on the author's profile

- Description
- Licenses – defaults to the most recent version of the internationally recognised Creative Commons, aligning with the expectations set out by the European Commission.

Basic information
>

Digital Object Identifier *

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes No

10.5281/zenodo.14269781 ✕

Reserve a DOI by pressing the button (so it can be included in files prior to upload). The DOI is registered when your upload is published.

Resource type *

Dataset

- Publication / Peer review
- Publication / Preprint
- Publication / Project deliverable
- Publication / Project milestone

Creators *

☰ De Leeuw, Marte (KU Leuven) Project member

Edit Remove

☰ Wyns, Roxanne (KU Leuven) Project member

Edit Remove

+ Add creator

Description

Paragraph B I

This document presents RESILIENCE's strategy and preparatory steps for developing a comprehensive service catalogue, focusing on integrating existing services from both the RESILIENCE headquarters and community (in-kind) contributions, other Research Infrastructures (RIs) and e-infrastructures. The Grant Agreement of the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project (PPP) specifies that the D2.1 Service Preparation and Implementation Strategy provides a "detailed description of the strategy for implementing RESILIENCE services". The final version of this deliverable is due in november 2025.

As an interim version, this document covers the work done by WP2 Services so far, including the findings and conclusions regarding the strategy, its guiding principles, initial steps towards a service catalogue, and the implementation of RESILIENCE as a distributed RI with a central hub and national nodes. It also outlines related policies and potential future steps. This deliverable serves as a guide during both current and future development of the complementary D2.2 User Services Catalogue. By implementing this strategy, we ensure that RESILIENCE remains at the forefront of supporting research within the SSH community.

+ Add description

Licenses

☰ **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**

The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited. [Read more](#)

Edit Remove

+ Add standard + Add custom

Add Recommended information

Fill in as much additional metadata as possible, even if it isn't required, to increase visibility:

- Contributors – again, use ORCID IDs to ensure the upload appears on the author's profile
- Keywords – type out multiple keywords for maximal discovery
- Languages
- Dates – these are useful when a deliverable is updated, submitted or accepted
- Publisher – automatically set to 'Zenodo,' only change this if the file was originally published (and still lives) on another platform

Tip: Be as clear and complete as possible. Accurate metadata ensures that your deliverable is indexed correctly and improves discoverability through Zenodo, EOSC, and external harvesters

RESILIENCE-specific Requirements

In case you are uploading a deliverable that has not been approved by the European Commission yet, add 'DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION' in the version field.

When adding a document that is a direct output of the RESILIENCE PPP, add a link to the correct – already existing (not custom) – award/grant, which in RESILIENCE's case has the DOI [10.3030/101079792](https://doi.org/10.3030/101079792)

Funding
▼

Awards/Grants

+ Add

+ Add custom

Add standard award/grant

101079792
Q

European Commission (BE) ✕

RESILIENCE PPP — RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project 101079792

European Commission

«
<
1
>
»

Did not find your award/grant? [Add a custom award/grant.](#)

✕ Cancel

✓ Add

Add Related works

If applicable, add related works, like in the example where the D2.1 Service Strategy references the D2.4 Data Management Plan. The 'Related works' will most likely – except for software – be the last field(s) you need to fill out for RESILIENCE deliverables.

Related works
▶

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type
References ✕	10.5281/zenodo.13939 ✕	DOI ✕	Publication / Project deliverable ✕

+ Add related work

Review and Submit

When all the information is filled out, you can save a draft and preview your record before submitting it for review by the RESILIENCE Data Unit.

Final Checklist

Before submitting, confirm that:

- ✓ Files are uploaded
- ✓ Description is clear and has no spelling mistakes
- ✓ Resource type = Project deliverable
- ✓ Version number included
- ✓ Draft warning added (if applicable)
- ✓ RESILIENCE PPP grant number is present
- ✓ Multiple keywords typed out
- ✓ Related works added (if relevant)
- ✓ Draft previewed

Support

For more information on metadata conventions, see the RESILIENCE [Data Management Plan](#) on Zenodo
For questions about Zenodo uploads to the RESILIENCE Community, contact resilience@fscire.it